

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY
Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya
University Research Center

I. Traditional Beliefs and Practices on Postpartum Care in a Rural Community in the Philippines: Towards a Multidisciplinary Practice of Postpartum Care

II. Project Description

In an earlier study that the researchers conducted about the perspectives on health and wellbeing of the Ilocanos in Northern Luzon, they found that postpartum care is laden with many traditional beliefs and practices. For the Ilocanos, traditional practices related to postpartum care are integrated in their observance of *tanggap*, the Ilocano term for postpartum care practices. Among all the traditional health beliefs and practices identified in the said study, beliefs and practices surrounding *tanggap* stood out which indicates that the Ilocanos take childbirth and postpartum care as a serious health condition. The result of the study inspired the researchers to do a follow up research on the traditional beliefs and practices surrounding postpartum care, highlighting the observation that these beliefs and practices may have implications on overall maternal health. It has been said that when a woman gives birth, half of her feet are already buried on the ground. What people did not know is that around “two-thirds of all maternal deaths occur during the postpartum period” in the Philippines (Yamashita, Suplido, Ladines-Llave, Tanaka, Senba, and Matsuo, 2014). This scenario still occurs despite the efforts of the health department to provide a holistic health care for all. What happens to the mother on the days and weeks after giving birth must then be given appropriate attention in order to facilitate a more responsive health care service to improve maternal health care.

III. Mechanism Applied: D

IV. Identified Research Agenda: Health and Wellness

V. Name of Proponents:

Lead Researcher: Dr. Clara M. Gonzales
Collaborators: Mrs. Rosalie C. Carreon
Mr. Brent Jericko P. Narciso
Dr. Zayda S. Asuncion

VI. Rationale

The inclusion of maternal death reduction as a major target between 1990 and 2015 in the United Nations' Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) made maternal care a global concern (WHO, 2018). The decision is a positive development, especially so that maternal death is still high in many countries. Beginning in 2000, the World Health Organization (WHO) has been circulating several guidelines and recommendations on maternal health care, including postnatal care elements. However, in its 2018 report on maternal health care among eight countries in the Western Pacific Region, WHO noted that “unnecessary or potentially harmful practices not recommended by WHO remain in many national protocols (p. vii),” including the Philippines.

In the Philippines, the Department of Health (DOH) is the agency tasked by the government to ensure that there is an effective maternal health care service to reduce maternal and neonatal complications and death. Unfortunately, one study found that “while various efforts are being undertaken to improve the implementation of maternal health program among pregnant women and immunization for children, there is a slow take up of these services” (Pambid, 2015, p. 16). It also appears that these government programs give more attention to pre-natal than post-natal period, which is still considered critical for the mother and her infant.

The postpartum period, also called postnatal or puerperal period, refers to the weeks immediately after a woman has given birth (Chou, 2017). In most cultures, this period is a time of social celebration for the arrival of a new baby and a time for the mother to recuperate. During this time, the woman recovers from the trauma of childbirth and embarks on her role as the primary caregiver of her infant through breastfeeding.

In the Philippines, postpartum care is given much importance by many cultural groups. Each culture has its own traditional prescriptions related to postpartum care which are usually

shared or passed on from one generation to the next. The pregnant woman is also prepared by briefing her of these practices during the months of her pregnancy.

One cultural group in the Philippines with a well-defined set of prescriptions related to postpartum care are the Ilocanos. *Tanggap*, or the Ilocano term for postpartum care, is laden with a lot of traditional beliefs and practices to ensure that the new mother recovers well. Understanding the Ilocano practices related to *tanggap* requires one to understand first the Ilocanos as a cultural group.

The Ilocanos are one of the largest ethnolinguistic groups in the Philippines (Ramos, 1990). They also exhibit a local diaspora by settling in different parts of the country, including Nueva Vizcaya. Given this fact, it is interesting to know how much of their culture, including their practice of *tanggap*, is retained in them as they faced the challenges of migration, modernization, and cultural diversity.

Several researches which documented traditional postpartum care practices and rituals around the world showed some similarities. One study revealed a high awareness and practice of traditional postpartum care, which is locally known in Malaysia as '*pantang*', among Malaysian women. In Malay, '*pantang*', which literally means restrictions, refers to the 'do's and don'ts' during the postpartum confinement period. Among the Malays, their postpartum practices range from prescribed confinement period, postpartum diet, massage, hot compress, corset, herbal baths and medicinal tonics as well as certain specific lifestyle measures (Hishamshah, bin Ramzan, Rashid, Wan Mustaffa, Haroon, and Badaruddin, 2010).

Another study noted the existence of postpartum practices in Southeast Asia, the Middle East, South America, and Africa (Dennis, Fung, Grigoriadis, Robinson, Romans, and Ross, 2007, in Chou, 2017). In 2007, Dennis and her team conducted a qualitative systematic review on traditional postpartum practices and rituals. They identified six themes to describe these practices: organized support, rest period and restricted activities, diet, hygiene practices, infant care and breastfeeding, and other postpartum rituals (Chou, 2017).

One particular study posed the question as to whether these traditional postpartum care practices are still workable despite the challenge of modernization (Gatan, 1990) and medical interventions to improve maternal care. Interestingly, several of these studies stressed the need to reconcile these traditional practices and scientific advancements related to postpartum care for a more effective and better maternal health care package (Pambid, 2015; Gatan, 1990; Dennis et al., 2007, in Chou, 2017).

While it is true that several postpartum healthcare services were spearheaded by the government, one study found that utilization of these services was inadequate, especially for women who delivered at home (Yamashita et al., 2014). In fact, one study mentioned that in developing countries, 70% of new mothers do not receive postpartum care from health care facilities. It is probably because of this why a number of traditional postpartum practices are commonly observed by new mothers (Hishamshah, et al., 2010).

In an earlier study (Gonzales, Asuncion, & Carreon, 2019) on the perspectives on health and wellbeing of the Ilocanos in Northern Luzon, one of its key findings was the prevalence of traditional beliefs and practices surrounding postpartum care, or *tanggap*. Most of the women interviewed in the study shared that it was during postpartum period that they mostly practiced traditional healing or medicines. Accordingly, such practices were passed on by the woman-elders such as mothers, aunts, grandparents, or mothers-in-law.

A similar study on '*tanggap*' as practiced by the Ilocano working mothers was also conducted by Gatan (1990). In the study, Gatan found that there are "traditional practices which are persistent through age and time but there are also various changes or modifications introduced for various reasons (p. 8)." However, even if she found that many commended the practice for its wholesomeness in providing psychosocial support to the mother and her infant, she also noted that some practices were discarded because such did not have any scientific basis at all.

It is in the light of the foregoing discussions that this study has been conceptualized. The main purpose of this study is to surface the traditional beliefs and practices in relation to postpartum care among Ilocano working mothers in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. Furthermore, to address the recommendations of the reviewed related studies, this present study also attempted to establish the medical value of *tanggap* by comparing it with the postnatal care guidelines advanced by the WHO, a global health organization, with the hope that culture and science could become partners in providing a competent maternal care. The WHO was sought because of its extensive effort to address universal health and wellbeing. Set up by the diplomats of the United Nations in 1945, the WHO is a global health organization whose constitution came into force on April 7, 1948 – a date annually celebrated as World Health Day (<https://www.who.int/about/who-we-are/history>). Committed to achieve better health for all,

WHO has spearheaded the crafting and adoption of various guidelines and recommendations on maternal healthcare over the years.

The findings can be a support to our health practitioners in understanding the role of culture and tradition in terms of how cultural groups perceive medical breakthroughs in relation to postpartum care. To borrow the words of Dennis et al. (2007, in Chou, 2017), "it is essential for physicians to understand how traditional postpartum beliefs play a role in culturally competent healthcare (p. 3)."

As for the immediate utilization of this study, results may be integrated in the subject Care of Mother, Child, and Adolescent offered among BS Nursing students. Also, the results will serve as the basis for the crafting of a health promotional material to advance postpartum care among mothers (Phase III of this project. Contents of the promotional material will be based on the findings of this present study.)

VII. Research Objective

General Objective:

The main objective of this study was to describe the beliefs and practices related to traditional postpartum care among Ilocano working mothers in a rural community in Northern Luzon, Philippines.

Specific Objectives:

Specifically, this study was guided by the following objectives:

1. To describe the beliefs and practices related to traditional postpartum care among Ilocano working mothers in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya;
2. To describe the challenges that Ilocano working mothers meet in their observance of their traditional postpartum practices; and
3. To determine the medical foundations of the traditional postpartum care practices.

VIII. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

As a cultural study, this is anchored on Culture Theory by Olivier Serrat, who defined culture as the "totality of a society's distinctive ideas, beliefs, values, and knowledge. It exhibits the ways humans interpret their environments" (Serrat, 2008, p. 1). Culture theory forwards the idea that societies were formed not because they are comprised of autonomous individuals who are free of social sanctions but because they are powered by social beings and their distinctive ideas, beliefs, values, and knowledge. It can contribute to understanding and promoting development where group relationships predominate and individualism is tempered. Approaches to cultural studies range widely, but some characteristics include the following: "they aim to examine their subject matter in terms of cultural practices and their relation to power; and they expose and attempt to reconcile knowledge divides to overcome the split between tacit cultural knowledge and objective (so-called universal) forms of knowledge (p. 2)."

Surfacing, therefore, the cultural practices of the Ilocanos in the context of "*tanggap*" gives us a glimpse of who they are as a people and the way they see the world. It gives us a picture of the things and values that they keep close to their heart, which strengthen their identity as one unique group with distinct practices, beliefs, and rituals to cope with the challenges of the world.

However, postpartum care is no longer just a cultural concern as it has evolved into a global health priority due to the high maternal deaths that we still experience up to this day. The integration of maternal death reduction in the development goals of many health organizations attests to the urgency of finding a solution to end the problem. With that, it is also the desire of this study to reconcile culture and science, and to find out in which space do the two meet at a most cordial level.

Therefore, this study is also anchored on a biomedical model, a research framework which aims to examine the effects of drugs and medical techniques on the biological systems of living creatures (Collins English Dictionary, 2019). Furthermore, the biomedical model of health is a scientific measure that doctors take in order to find out reasons behind a particular disease (What is biomedical model of health, 2019).

Along this line, the medical model of health also serves as a framework for this study. The medical model of health describes the approach to illness which is dominant in Western medicine. It treats the human body as a very complex mechanism and advocates the treatment of symptoms through the use of medical intervention and procedures (Lesson elements, 2012). It is but fitting then for this study to also take into consideration the United Nations' Millennium Development Goals aimed at reducing maternal deaths and the World Health Organization's Sustainable Development Goals as embodied in its guidelines and recommendations on maternal health care.

Figure 1. Paradigm of the study

First, the beliefs and practices related to postpartum care among Ilocano working mothers in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya are determined. The purpose of such is to ascertain which among the traditional practices on postpartum care have survived the test of time, migration, and modernization.

Second, the challenges that these women encounter in their observance of their traditional beliefs and practices on postpartum care are identified. Since the respondents are Ilocano working mothers, they might have unique experiences that challenge their observance of their cultural practices on postpartum care.

Third, the prevailing traditional postpartum care practices are compared with the postnatal care recommendation from the World Health Organization, a global health organization widely known for its efforts to advance health and wellbeing for all.

This study has several cultural and clinical implications, as results may be integrated in the subject Care of Mother, Child, and Adolescent offered among BS Nursing students. Also, the results will serve as the basis in the crafting of health promotional materials to advance postpartum care among mothers. (*Phase III of this project*).

Scope and Delimitation

This study looked into the traditional beliefs and practices on postpartum care of Ilocano working mothers in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. Since the Ilocanos in Nueva Vizcaya, specifically those who reside in the capital town of Bayombong, have formed one Ilocano variety, some of the practices mentioned in this paper may show variations from the practices of other Ilocano varieties in other parts of the Philippines. Data were gathered through a simple survey among Ilocano working mothers. The medical foundations of these practices were based on the recommendation advanced by the World Health Organization in its 2013 and 2015 postnatal care guidelines. Due to the limitation posed by the Covid-19 pandemic, the original plan to interview health professionals was not carried out. Only Ilocano working mothers who have given birth and who have undergone *tanggad* were included in the simple survey, regardless of their civil status and number of children. Only traditional beliefs and practices surrounding postpartum care were gathered, and did not include other cultural beliefs and practices before and during the actual birth.

Research Significance

This study is of significance to the following:

For *healthcare providers*, findings of the study may provide them additional information as to how postpartum care are viewed and practiced by mothers. Results of the study may be used to explain the success or failure of certain health-related campaigns on maternal care, or why some government-backed health-related practices have been rejected by cultural groups.

For the *Department of Health* and other health policymakers, findings of the study may bring to light the role of culture in having a healthy nation. The results of the study may be considered when policies on maternal health are made. This particular need is also expressed in several studies on postpartum care reviewed for this study.

For *Ilocano women*, results of the study may provide them new ideas that will help them come to terms with their traditional beliefs and practices on postpartum care. It will provide them better understanding of the scientific and medical foundations of their cultural beliefs and practices in relation to postpartum care. This way, it is expected that they take an active role in making decisions as to the kind of maternal care that they should receive after giving birth.

For other *researchers*, findings of the study may serve as their basis when they embark on researches about the interplay between culture and science especially in relation to healthcare.

Definition of Terms

Biomedical model refers to a research framework which aims to examine the effects of drugs and medical techniques on the biological systems of living creatures (Collins English Dictionary, 2019). In this study, biomedical model of postpartum care refers to the integration of the medical foundations of the Ilocano traditional beliefs and practices on postpartum care.

Postpartum care refers to the process of recovery that a woman goes through after giving birth. It usually has several areas of concern, such as but not limited to, dietary modification, massage, bathing requirements, corset or binder, herbal application and lifestyle changes. In this study, postpartum care is also referred to as "*tanggad*", the Ilocano term for postpartum care.

Medical model of health describes the approach to illness which is dominant in Western medicine. It treats the human body as a very complex mechanism and advocates the treatment of symptoms through the use of medical intervention and procedures (Models of health, 2019). This is one of the scientific frameworks where this present study is anchored.

Multidisciplinary health care practice refers to the integrated way of practicing healthcare, where recognized healthcare practitioners and cultural bearers come together and become partners in promoting maternal healthcare.

Recognized Health care practitioners are people who are medically licensed to practice healthcare like nurses, RHU staffs, and doctors. Their knowledge and expertise on healthcare have been acquired through education or special training.

Traditional beliefs and practices on postpartum care refer to the customs and behaviors surrounding the postpartum period, or the confinement period after a woman has given birth. In concept, beliefs and practices are difficult to separate because people's beliefs are reflected in their practices. In this study, these beliefs and practices on postpartum care may or may not have scientific or medical value. These traditional beliefs and practices are usually observed when taking care of a woman who has just given birth to keep her body healthy and strong.

IX. Related Literature and Studies

Traditional Practices on Postpartum Care

Across the world, the postpartum period is a sensitive time for the mother-infant unit and her family. Way before scientific methods of promoting maternal care were advanced, many traditional practices are already applied to protect the health of the mother and the baby. These traditions and rituals are deeply rooted in people's cultures that is why many of these practices are very much alive even up to this day.

In Turkey, Altuntug, Anik and Ege (2018) found that traditional practices towards mother care in the period after birth are common. Data were gathered in 2015 from 291 women who visited family health centers at the first eight weeks of postpartum period. Based on the results, the majority of their respondents applied a traditional mother care practice during the postpartum period, ranging from practices for increasing breast milk and preventing postpartum bleeding.

If the Malays call the postpartum period "*pantang*", for the Chinese, they call the one month postpartum period '*zuo yuezi*', whose literal translation means "doing the month". '*Zuo yuezi*' is commonly practiced in urban and rural families to help the mother regain her strength and protect her future health. The study of Raven, Chen, Tolhurst, and Garner in 2007 surfaced several postpartum practices, which were categorized into three: dietary precautions, behavioral precautions, and hygiene. Dietary precautions include the following: eating more food, eating "hot" food (protein rich), and avoiding "cold" food (fruit and vegetables). Behavioral precautions include the following: staying inside the home, avoiding housework, resting in bed, abstaining from sex, and limiting visitors. Hygiene prescriptions include not bathing or washing of hair, washing of the vulval and perineal area every day, and not brushing of teeth (Raven, Chen, Tolhurst, & Garner, 2007). Accordingly, the Chinese subscribed to these practices mainly because of respect for tradition and to follow the advice of elders.

In the Philippines, Bermio and Reotutar (2017) determined the extent of beliefs and practices during the whole process of pregnancy, childbirth, and infant care of women who sought prenatal check-up, consultation, confined, and delivered at the Ilocos Sur District Hospital in Narvacan, Ilocos Sur in 2016. In the study, the respondents manifested a high extent of beliefs. In terms of postpartum care, the study found that women generally agreed to the belief that a woman should not take in cold drinks after giving birth so that she will not chill easily.

Among the Aetas living in Central Philippines, boiled leaves of plants are used by the mother on her first bath two to three weeks after giving birth to avoid relapse (Grey, 2016).

It must be noted that most of the studies conducted on postpartum care did not find any direct relationship between the practice and the speedy recovery of the mother. What was evident though was the psychosocial support that these traditional practices afforded to the new mother. Several studies even linked the traditional practices with the mitigation of postpartum depression. Along this line, one study examined the research literature investigating the effects of postpartum rituals on postpartum depression (Grigoriadis, Robinson, Fung, Ross, Chee, Dennis, and Romans (2009). The study included 12 qualitative and quantitative studies that focused on traditional practices and rituals in the postpartum period, and their relation to postpartum depression or mood. In the systematic review, the researchers posited that there was no clear evidence as to the relation between carrying out traditional postpartum rituals and the occurrence of postpartum depression. However, the body of studies examined provided enough evidence to suggest that the key protective element of the traditional practices against postpartum depression is the presence of social support rather than the specific ritual.

The effect of cultural rituals during the postpartum period goes beyond physical recovery. In one literature review, it was found that postpartum depression could be mitigated by cultural practices, such as resting for a period of time after giving birth, observing a diet and other restrictions, and receiving support from the extended family (usually the mother or mother-in-law) (Bina, 2005).

Challenges that Influence the Continuance of Traditional Practices on Postpartum Care

Postpartum care practices, whether traditional or supported by Western medicine, are one in terms of objective, and that is to make the recovery fast and easy for the new mother. But despite this similarity of objective, not all traditional practices are supported by modern medicine.

Raven, Chen, Tolhurst, and Garner (2007) found in their study that some traditional postpartum practices are beneficial to the mother and baby, whereas other practices are not or do not have any obvious health effect. Compared against Western medical standards, several traditional postpartum practices are beneficial, including eating more, eating protein-rich food, avoiding housework, and daily vulval and perineal hygiene as these practices are also proven by scientific studies to speed up the new mother's recovery. A few are potentially harmful, including avoiding dental hygiene as it allows a buildup of plaque and bacteria that can cause teeth decay. Some practices that do not have obvious effects according to the Western health model are avoiding cold food (fruit and vegetables), staying inside the house, and not bathing or washing of hair.

Bermio and Reotutar (2017) recommend that health programs conducted by the health department should give emphasis on what beliefs and practices are beneficial to both the mother and the child, and that implications of the non-scientific practices should be explained well to them. They also recommend that further research be conducted to evaluate whether these beliefs and practices promote health and whether these bring risks to the mother-child unit.

Altuntug, Anik and Ege (2018), who determined the traditional practices of mother care in the postpartum period in Turkey, stressed on the importance of understanding the traditional beliefs and practices of the individuals, families, and society by health professionals so that they can provide better health services.

In the study of Grey in 2016 about the cultural beliefs and practices of Aetas living in Central Philippines, she found that it was during pregnancy that the Aetas mostly practiced their old beliefs and practices. However, despite the fact that their cultural practices are deeply rooted in their beliefs since it has already been part of their tradition for years, Grey also found that these practices are greatly influenced by modernization, media, and technology.

In the Philippines, Yamashita, et al. (2014) demonstrated inadequate utilization of postpartum health care services, both in terms of access to care and utilization of postpartum services. Accordingly, this is especially true for women who delivered at home. They also demonstrated that postpartum women lacked knowledge about potential postpartum health issues identified as crucial by the health sector and international organizations like the WHO.

In the 2017 National Demographic and Health Survey carried out by the Philippine Statistics Authority, it appears that Filipino mothers now realize that postpartum care helps prevent complications after childbirth. The number of mothers receiving a postnatal check within two days of delivery is increasing, while only a few percentage did not have a postnatal check within 41 days of delivery.

The aforementioned studies provide support to the idea that traditional practices on postpartum care must also be assessed in the context of Western medicine. While it is true that traditional practice in any form shapes the cultural identity of a group of people, its soundness must also be given a second look

especially if it poses danger to the wellbeing of the cultural bearers.

Synthesis

The prevalence of traditional practices related to postpartum care in many cultures is documented in many studies. There is a clear evidence to conclude that cultural practices are still very much alive in today's generation. These traditional practices only prove the attention and concern that different cultures afford to the mother-infant unit. In a way, this is expected since the whole process of childbirth, including the days and months after delivery, is a crucial stage for the mother and her infant especially that several maternal deaths have also been documented. These maternal death incidents, and other maternal care issues like postpartum depression, prompted different health organizations to lay down prescriptions to improve maternal care. Unfortunately, some of the prescriptions based on Western medicine do not support certain traditional practices which are already integrated in the identity of various cultures. There are many cultural studies on traditional postpartum practices, but only few studies dwelt on how to reconcile traditional and scientific prescriptions in order to achieve a culturally competent and scientifically sound practice. This is the gap that this research wishes to fill.

X. Methodology

Research Design

Quantitative and qualitative approaches of research were used in this study. As a quantitative study, a checklist of practices was used to surface the traditional Ilocano practices on postpartum care. Similar process was also used to determine the challenges that the respondents encountered in their observance of such practice. To describe such practices, results were quantified before these were interpreted. As a qualitative study, the direct statements from the respondents were used to provide further support to the quantitative data gathered.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. As the capital of Nueva Vizcaya, Bayombong is home to many local migrants including those who identified themselves as Ilocanos. Bayombong is composed of 25 barangays. It is a first class municipality which, according to the 2010 NSO survey, has a total land area of 16, 165 hectares and with 57,416 total populations (Nueva Vizcaya website). It is also the home of several cultural groups such as the Gaddangs and Isinays. Local migrants include the Ifugaos, Ilocanos, Kankanaeys, among others.

Respondents/Informants of the Study

The main respondents of the study were the Ilocano working mothers who have already practiced "*tanggap*" in their postpartum recovery, regardless of the years that have passed since they gave birth. Because they are currently employed, it is assumed that their memory is still sharp given also the fact that childbirth experience is a milestone in a woman's life which cannot be easily forgotten. Working mothers were chosen as respondents because of their education and schedule as dictated by their work. These factors may have influenced the way they practiced traditional postpartum care. Purposive sampling was used to determine the respondents. A total of 50 respondents were tapped after they were affirmative on the following qualifications:

1. They identify themselves as Ilocano;
2. They have given birth and practiced, or continue to practice, the Ilocano postpartum care "*tanggap*"; and
3. They are employed in a legitimate organization (public or private).

The respondents were teachers, medical practitioners, government employees, and support staff of various establishments in Bayombong and nearby towns. The youngest respondent was 24 years old and the oldest was 66. In terms of the number of children, it ranged from 1 to 5 children. An informed consent was also signed by the respondents.

Data Gathering Tools

A. Survey Checklist

A simple survey checklist was administered among the respondents in order to surface their traditional beliefs and practices on postpartum care, and the challenges that they encountered in their observance of such practices.

The survey checklist is composed of six elements of care featuring the traditional Ilocano

practices on postpartum care, with multi-numbered possible reasons for doing the practice, and four items about the challenges in the observance of *tanggap*, with multi-numbered possible reasons for each challenge. The checklist was adopted from the study of Gatan (1990).

B. Online Research

Once the traditional beliefs and practices on postpartum care as well as the challenges for the continued practice were established, an online research was done utilizing medical books and research journals to look for the medical foundations of these practices. The purpose of such is to reconcile culture and science so that culturally sensitive and scientifically sound maternal health care is provided. In the end, the researchers settled to use the postnatal care recommendations advanced by the WHO because of the organization's scope and extent of research.

Data Gathering Procedure

To surface the traditional beliefs and practices on postpartum care, as well as the challenges that the respondents encountered in their observance of such practices, a simple survey checklist was administered among Ilocano working mothers who have practiced traditional postpartum care or *tanggap*. The respondents were purposively chosen, taking into consideration the pre-determined inclusion criteria of the respondents. Since one of the inclusion criteria is being employed in a private or public organization, the researchers targeted the different organizations in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya in looking for respondents. Establishments were first identified then the researchers looked for employees that fit the pre-determined qualifications. Because the data gathering period was interrupted by the pandemic, some respondents answered the survey checklist online. The researchers also resorted to the recommendations of their colleague or of other respondents in looking for more respondents. After the data were gathered, simple frequency count and percent were used to organize data. Once the prevailing practices and challenges were identified, the researchers proceeded to the next step of determining the medical foundations of such practices by comparing the traditional practices with the postnatal care guidelines recommended by the World Health Organization.

Analysis of Data

To surface the common traditional beliefs and practices on postpartum care, as well as the challenges, simple frequency count and percentage were used.

XI. Results and Discussion

Ilocano postpartum care practices

Like in any culture, child birth is a major event among the Ilocanos. The arrival of a new baby brings both excitement to the family and concern for the overall condition of both the mother and child. In most instances, the recovery of the mother is given much attention because of two major reasons: her body went through the trauma of childbirth and no one else can perform breastfeeding except her. Since the pains of labor, childbirth, and breastfeeding cannot be passed on to any one, the physical recovery of the mother becomes a family concern to assure her that she is not alone in this journey. Even months before the actual childbirth, the husband or the elder woman in the family, usually the mother or mother-in-law, already prepares the postnatal care that would be afforded to both the mother and the baby. During this time, traditional practices on postpartum care are reviewed to make sure that nothing would be missed.

For the Ilocanos in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, their postpartum care practices, or *tanggap*, could be observed in five areas of concern: on physical setting, on what to use, on physical hygiene on what to take in, and on maintenance of energy (Gatan, 1990). Below is a summary of these practices:

The physical setting where the new mother stays after childbirth is meticulously prepared. She stays in a dark room with little ventilation to prevent the occurrence of gastric disorder and beri-beri, to enable the return of normal skin color, and to prevent one from relapsing. A stove (*dalican*) is placed nearby to warm her from time to time. This is done to prevent the occurrence of gastric disorders and beri-beri, to drive evil spirits away, and to neutralize the odor emitted during delivery.

Aside from preparing the place where the woman stays after birth, there are also prescriptions about what to wear during the confinement period. She is asked to cover up her body by wearing long skirts, pajama, shawl (*rutap*), and *bandana* to facilitate convenience in breastfeeding and in changing clothes and to prevent the penetration of air into the pores thus preventing the development of varicose veins and *rayuma*. She is also asked to wear a belt (*barikis*) around the stomach/abdomen for at least five months and a belt or girdle (*patapat/it-it*) around the lower hips for at least three months. Accordingly, this is done to prevent the occurrence of abdominal and back pains, to prevent gastric disorders, to

prevent excessive blood flow, to prevent the mother from bleeding profusely, and to help regain the normal shape of the body. The woman also wears a piece of cloth tied around the forehead to help sustain strength especially right after delivery, to prevent dizziness and to prevent involuntary nodding of head.

From the day of giving birth to the 9th day, the mother is bathed with water whose heat she can tolerate to prevent impurities from rushing to the head, to serve as body regulator, and to keep the body fresh from the odor emitted by the genitals. From the 10th to the 14th day, the head and body are bathed to allow blood regulation and for the body to adapt to normal body temperature. She refrains from bathing on the 15th – 16th day (*tinnib*) to adjust oneself to temperature and to keep body heat regulated. She bathes with cold water on the 17th day to allow for return to usual hygienic routine and to test the body for any allergies. From day of delivery to the 17th day following delivery, she bathes with water nourished with herbs like *dangla* and guava to prevent one from relapsing, to facilitate healing of the uterus, and to serve as soothing balm for the skin.

The mother's dietary requirements are also looked into during her confinement period. She is asked to drink lukewarm water nourished with herbs (*subusob*, *pan-nig-an*, *putong balat*) from day of delivery to utmost 15 days for easy healing or internal wound, to prevent gastric pain, and to provide strength. She drinks water only regularly and does not go beyond what is prescribed to prevent vomiting and frequent urinating which might cause the *butilaw* (uterus) to come out. She eats *malunggay* dipped in salt from day of delivery to utmost two days. She eats foods rich in vitamins especially lean meat, stew, and *tulya* to stimulate the mammary glands for abundant milk supply for the baby, to keep her strong and to regain usual her health. She refrains from eating foods which are sour to prevent gastritis and to prevent clotting of blood impurities. It is also believed that sour foods eaten by the mother may cause baby's stomach ache. Aside from sour foods, she also refrains from eating foods which cause itch like *gabi*, *labong*, or any food seasoned with *bagoong*. She does this for at least 5-7 months to keep her skin clean and to prevent the occurrence of skin disorders and vaginal itch. She also refrains from eating ripened *langka* or jackfruit for at least a year to prevent urinary tract infection, to keep urine from emitting foul odor, and to keep one from relapsing. Foods with heavy protein contents like eggplant, coconut, *linga*, or peanuts are also avoided to prevent the occurrence of *beri-beri* for both the mother and baby and to facilitate proper digestion. It is also believed that eating these foods causes the uterus (*butilaw*) to come out.

To maintain energy, the mother is massaged with oil by the *hilot* on areas like the abdomen, hands, feet, back and the veins from the day of delivery and before taking a bath to facilitate the normal position of the ovary and to refresh the veins and muscles stretched during delivery. She is asked to take a complete rest by avoiding activities like reading, sewing, carrying of anything heavy, or doing any routine work to keep her from relapsing, to prevent her from becoming blind, and to help regain her usual strength.

Other postpartum care practices of the Ilocanos in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya include maintaining erect posture especially when eating to prevent the development of an unbalanced figure and to soothe muscles after going through childbirth. She also practices *sidor* or *su-ub* to regulate body heat and to serve as a soothing balm especially on the genitals.

These are the traditional belief and practices related to *tanggap* by the Ilocanos in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya.

Ilocano Working Mothers' Adherence to Tanggad or Postpartum Care

The Ilocanos are one of the ethno-linguistic groups which are widely dispersed in the Philippines. As a result, different varieties of Ilocanos settled in many regions, including Nueva Vizcaya. A good number of residents in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya identify themselves as Ilocanos. These Ilocanos may have found their way to Nueva Vizcaya due to common migration reasons like intercultural marriages, work, and better opportunities, among others.

For the Ilocanos in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, the continued practice of their tradition is challenged obviously by the diversity of culture in Bayombong, which is a home to many other indigenous groups like the Gaddangs, Isinays, and Ifugaos. Alongside this cultural diversity are the social and economic transformations that the Ilocano women go through. The empowerment of the Ilocano women could be observed in their sustained education and employment.

To describe the traditional beliefs and practices related to *tanggap* among the Ilocano working mothers in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, five areas of the concern were looked into, namely practices on physical setting, on what to use, on physical hygiene, on what to take in, on maintenance of energy, and other practices.

Table 1

Postpartum care practices on physical setting

On physical setting	Frequency (N=50)	Percent
A. Stays in a room that is dark, with curtains undrawn and with only little air/wind coming in...	32	64%
1. To prevent the occurrence of gastric disorders/discomfort	9	28
2. To prevent the occurrence of beri-beri (<i>ib-bal</i>)	5	16
3. To enable the return to normalcy of skin color	9	28
4. To prevent one from relapsing	14	44
5. Other reasons	2	6
6. I do not observe this.	18	36%
B. Has a stove (<i>dalican</i>) nearby where she can get herself warmed from time to time	19	38%
1. To prevent the occurrence of gastric disorders/discomfort	14	74
2. To prevent the occurrence of beri-beri (<i>ib-bal</i>)	1	5
3. To drive devil spirits away	3	16
4. To neutralize the odor emitted during delivery	2	11
5. Other reasons	2	11
6. I do not observe this.	31	62%

As shown in the table above, the preparation of the physical setting for postpartum care is still adhered to by the respondents, especially staying in a dark room with little ventilation (64%), but not much in having a *dalican* nearby to warm herself (38%). This is probably because nowadays, only few households use *dalicans* in cooking food. *Dalican*, which is the present counterpart of a gas stove or an induction stove, uses firewood or coal to start a fire for cooking or heating. Many households now do not have *dalicans* due to the inconvenience of its use, and modern way of cooking is afforded even by low-income households. The absence of a *dalican* in the house and the inconvenience of its use are probably reasons why this postpartum care prescription is not observed by the respondents. In fact, many of the respondents said that they are not aware of this practice or do not believe in its effectiveness.

R28: *No stove and not a family practice.*

R24: *I am not aware of this practice.*

R2: *Never heard this kind of postpartum care.*

Among those who practiced staying in a dark room with little ventilation, they said that they did this primarily to prevent one from relapsing (44%). There is also a belief that that exposure to light and air after childbirth can cause other adverse physical conditions such as gastric disorder and *beri-beri*.

Table 2

Postpartum care practices on what to use

On what to use	Frequency (N=50)	Percent
A. Uses long skirt and long sleeved blouse, pajama, shawl (<i>rutap</i>) and bandana or head gear...	44	88%
1. To facilitate convenience in breastfeeding	18	41
2. To facilitate convenience in changing clothes	15	34
3. To prevent the penetration of air into the pores thus preventing development of varicose veins and/or <i>rayuma</i> .	29	66
4. Other reasons	2	6
5. I do not observe this.	6	12%
B. Wears belt (<i>barikis/calso</i>) for the stomach/abdomen which she uses for at least five months, and a belt/girdle (<i>patapat/it-it</i>) for the lower hips which she ideally uses for three months.	43	86%
1. To prevent the occurrence of abdominal and back pains	18	42
2. To prevent gastric disorders/disturbances especially since the baby has just been delivered	8	19
3. To prevent blood from flowing excessively	5	12
4. To prevent the mother from bleeding profusely	9	21

5. To help regain the normal shape of one's body	27	63
6. Other reasons.	1	2
7. I do not observe this.	7	14%
C. Wears a piece of cloth tied around the forehead	20	40%
1. To help sustain strength especially right after delivery	4	20
2. To prevent dizziness thereby helping in the maintenance of body equilibrium	8	40
3. To prevent involuntary "nodding" of head	11	55
4. Other reasons	2	1
5. I do not observe this.	30	60%

In terms of clothes worn by the new mother after giving birth, many of the respondents still adhered to the practice of covering up the body with extra clothing like shawl (*rutap*), long skirts, long sleeved blouses and pajamas (88%) primarily to hinder the penetration of air into the pores thus preventing the development of varicose veins and/or *rayuma* (66%). The adherence to this practice is in consonance with their practice of staying in a dark room with little ventilation as stated above.

Less than three-fourths (63%) of the respondents practiced the wearing of belt (*barikis/calso*) for the stomach or abdomen and belt or girdle (*patapat/it-it*) for the lower hips for several months after childbirth primarily to help regain the normal shape of one's body (86%). The woman's body goes through many physical changes during the nine months of pregnancy. For the woman, one manifestation of physical recovery from childbirth is getting back to her normal shape before her pregnancy.

The wearing of a piece of cloth tied around the forehead is not very much adhered to (40%). Many of the respondents said that they did not practice such because they were not told by their elders about it, and it was awkward to use one.

R37: Elders did not introduce this practice to me.

R27: It's awkward.

R1: My mother did not tell me about it.

Table 3

Postpartum care practices on physical hygiene

On physical hygiene	Frequency (N=50)	Percent
A. From the day of giving birth to the 9th day, the body is bathed with water whose heat she can tolerate	42	84%
1. To prevent impurities from rushing to the head	3	7%
2. To serve as body regulator	13	31%
3. For personal hygiene (keep body fresh from odor emitted by the genitals)	30	71%
4. Other reasons	1	2
5. I do not observe this.	8	16%
B. From the 10th to the 14th day, the head and body are bathed	38	76%
1. To allow blood regulation	8	21
2. Adaption of the body to normal/usual body temperature	30	79
3. Other reasons	3	8
4. I do not observe this.	12	24%
C. Refrains from bathing on the 15th -16th days ("tinnib")	24	48%
1. To adjust oneself to temperature	12	50
2. To keep body heat regulated	8	33
3. Other reasons	3	13
4. I do not observe this.	26	52%
D. Bathes with cold water on the 17th day	28	56%
1. To allow for return to usual hygienic routine	21	75
2. To test the body for any allergies	5	18
3. Other reasons	2	7
4. I do not observe this.	22	44%
E. From day of delivery to the 17th day following delivery, she bathes with water nourished with herbs or <i>talbos</i> (like dangla, guava, etc.)	39	78%

1. To prevent one from relapsing	20	51
2. To facilitate healing effect on uterus	19	49
3. To serve as soothing balm for the skin	21	54
4. Other reasons	5	13
5. I do not observe this.	11	22%

In term of physical hygiene, more than three-fourths of the respondents adhered to the practices of bathing only the body for nine days with water whose heat they can tolerate (84%), bathing with water nourished with herbs like *dangla* and guava from the day of delivery to the 17th day following delivery (78%), and bathing the head and body from the 10th to the 14th day (76%) following delivery. More than half of the respondents adhered to bathing with cold water on the 17th day (56%) and less than half refrained from bathing on the 15th-16th day (48%). Among all the postpartum care prescriptions related to *tanggap*, the bathing requirements are the most meticulous when it comes to timing of practice. The reasons for the continued practice of such prescriptions also vary, such as personal hygiene, soothing relief for the skin, adaption of the body to normal temperature, among others. It was noted that most of the reasons provided for observing such practices revolved around the woman's hygiene and physical convenience, and not so much for the baby's welfare, as emphasized in some health campaigns. Using of hot or lukewarm water nourished with herbs and refraining from washing the head or hair appeared to be a common bathing prescription adhered to by the respondents. The use of herbal plants to treat various medical conditions by cultural groups are well documented in many studies (Grey, 2016; Hishamshah, bin Ramzan, Rashid, Wan Mustaffa, Haroon, and Badaruddin, 2010), so it is not surprising at all if the Ilocano working mothers continue to adopt this. In contrast, using cold water when bathing during the confinement period and skipping bathing even for a few days only did not sit well with the respondents. Ironically, many cited doctor's advice as reasons for not adhering to the practice.

R11: *Doctors advise I go back to normal showering*

R29: *Warm water is needed for the pores.*

Table 4
Postpartum care practices on what to take in

On what to take in	Frequency (N=50)	Percent
A. Drinks lukewarm water nourished with herbs (<i>pan-nig-an, subusob, putong balat</i>) from day of delivery to utmost 15 days	31	62%
1. For easy healing of internal wound	20	65
2. To prevent gastric pain	16	52
3. To provide strength	10	32
4. Other reasons	1	3
5. I do not observe this.	19	38%
B. Drinks water only regularly (does not go beyond what is prescribed)	25	50%
1. To prevent vomiting	11	44
2. To prevent body tissues	3	12
3. To prevent frequent urinating which might cause the " <i>butilaw</i> " to come out	12	48
4. Other reasons	6	24
5. I do not observe this.	25	50%
C. From day of delivery to utmost two days, she eats malunggay dipped in salt	34	68%
1. To nourish the mammary glands	17	50
2. To supply vitamin to both the mother and the baby	22	44
3. To prevent occurrence of beri-beri (<i>ib-bal</i>)	8	24
4. Other reasons	0	0
5. I do not observe this.	16	32%
D. Eats foods rich in vitamins especially lean meat, stew, tulya, etc.	47	94%
1. To stimulate the secretion of the mammary glands	30	64
2. To provide full nourishment to the baby	16	47
3. To keep one strong	22	47
4. To help regain usual strength	26	55
5. Other reasons	2	4

On what to take in	Frequency (N=50)	Percent
6. I do not observe this.	3	6%
E. Refrains from eating foods which are sour	35	70%
1. To prevent gastritis	20	57
2. It may cause baby's stomachache	15	43
3. To prevent clotting of blood impurities (<i>lurayen</i>)	6	17
4. Other reasons	1	3
5. I do not observe this.	15	30%
F. Refrains from eating foods which cause itch like <i>gabi</i> , <i>labong</i> (for at least 5-7 months respectively) or any food seasoned with <i>bagoong</i> .	41	82%
1. To keep skin clean	3	7
2. To prevent occurrence of skin disorders	13	32
3. To prevent occurrence of vaginal itch	31	76
4. Other reasons	2	5
5. I do not observe this.	9	18%
G. Refrains from eating ripened <i>langka</i> or jackfruit, preferably for a year	36	72%
1. To prevent urinary tract infection	1	3
2. To keep urine from emitting foul odor	28	78
3. To keep one from relapsing	4	11
4. Other reasons	6	17
5. I do not observe this.	14	28%
H. Refrains from eating eggplant and coconut, <i>linga</i> , peanuts or any food with heavy protein contents.	27	54%
1. It causes the uterus to come out (<i>butilaw</i>)	10	42
2. To prevent occurrence of <i>bri-beri</i> on both mother and the baby	11	41
3. To facilitate proper digestion	4	15
4. Other reasons	4	15
5. I do not observe this.	23	46%

Among all the traditional practices related to *tanggad*, it is the woman's dietary requirement that has the most number of proscriptions probably because of the belief that everything that she takes in goes directly to her body and is passed on to her baby through breastfeeding. Among the dietary prescriptions, it is eating foods rich in vitamins like lean meat, stew and *tulya* that is adhered to by almost all of the respondents (47 out of 50) or 94%. More than half of the respondents adhered to the following food prescriptions: eating *malunggay* dipped in salt from the day of delivery up to two days (68%), drinking lukewarm water nourished with herbs (*pan-nig-an*, *subusob*, *putong balat*) from day of delivery to utmost 15 days (62%), and drinking water only regularly, not going beyond what is prescribed (50%). A large majority of the respondents also adhered to the different food proscriptions, such as avoidance of foods that cause itch like *gabi*, *labong* or any food seasoned with *bagoong* for 5-7 months (82%), ripened *langka* or jackfruit, preferably for a year (72%), and sour food (70%). Based on the proscriptions, not all foods are safe to be eaten by the mother during the postpartum period. Their reasons for following these dietary food prescriptions and proscriptions are for ease of breastfeeding, healing of the vaginal wound, cleansing of the internal and external reproductive organs, and preventing stomach discomforts for the mother and the baby.

Table 5

Postpartum care practices on maintenance of energy

On maintenance of energy	Frequency	Percent
A. From day of delivery and henceforth before taking a bath, she is massaged with oil by the <i>hilot</i> , especially on areas like the abdomen, hands, feet, back and also the veins	39	78%
1. To facilitate the normal position of the ovary	16	41
2. To refresh the veins and muscles stretched during delivery	33	85
3. Other reasons	2	5
4. I do not observe this.	11	28%
B. Takes complete rest (avoids reading, sewing, carrying of anything heavy,	48	96%

routine work)		
1. To keep one from relapsing	21	44
2. To prevent one from becoming blind (<i>ar-rap</i>)	16	33
3. Helps one to easily regain usual strength	29	60
4. Other reasons	1	2
5. I do not observe this.	2	4%

To maintain energy, almost all (96%) of the respondents adhered to taking a complete rest by avoiding reading, sewing, routine work, and carrying of anything heavy. Of this number, more than half (60%) said that taking a complete rest helps them from regaining their usual strength. Others reasoned out that complete rest keeps one from relapsing (44%) and prevents one from becoming blind (33%). This is not surprising at all because childbirth requires medical attention. The confinement period after childbirth is recognized by most cultural communities and by global health organizations as a time for the woman to physically recuperate. During this time, household chores are delegated to other members of the family, and if ever the mother carries anything, it should only be her baby.

Being massaged by a *hilot* from the day of delivery and before taking a bath is also a common practice, adhered to by 78% of the respondents. It is believed that this practice refreshes the veins and muscles stretched during delivery (33 out of 39) and facilitates the normal position of the ovary (16 out of 39). This particular practice also surfaced in other cultural groups in the Philippines and even in other Asian countries (Hishamshah, bin Ramzan, Rashid, Wan Mustaffa, Haroon, and Badaruddin, 2010).

Table 6

Other postpartum care practices

Other practices	Frequency (N=50)	Percent
A. Maintains erect posture especially when eating (feet together on level position and with the back straight)	35	70%
1. Prevents development of an unbalanced figure	20	57
2. Soothes muscles especially since mother gets tired easily following delivery	20	57
3. Other reasons	2	6
4. I do not observe this.	15	30%
B. Practices <i>sidor</i> or <i>su-ub</i>	35	70%
1. It serves as soothing balm especially on the genitals	17	49
2. To help regulate body heat	17	49
3. Other reasons	1	3
4. I do not observe this.	15	30%

Other postpartum care practices like maintaining erect posture especially when eating and practicing *sidor* or *su-ob* are adhered to by almost three-fourths of the respondents (70% each). Accordingly, erect posture is achieved when the feet are put together on level position and with the back straight primarily to prevent the development of an unbalanced state (57%) and to soothe muscles (57%). The maintenance of an erect posture is a physical manifestation of recovery from childbirth.

The practice of *sidor* or *su-ub* is done to regulate body heat (49%) and to serve a soothing balm especially on the genitals (49%).

The traditional postpartum care practices are also summarized in Table 7 to determine the practices adhered to by most of the respondents. All in all, there are 22 practices.

Table 7

Traditional postpartum care practices adhered to by most respondents

Traditional Postpartum Care Practices	Frequency (N=50)	Percent
1. Takes complete rest (avoids reading, sewing, carrying of anything heavy, routine work)	48	96%
2. Eats foods rich in vitamins especially lean meat, stew, tulya, etc.	47	94%
3. Uses long skirt and long sleeved blouse, pajama, shawl (<i>rutap</i>) and bandana or head gear.	44	88%
4. Wears belt (<i>barikis/calso</i>) for the stomach/abdomen which she uses for at least five months, and a belt/girdle (<i>patapat/it-it</i>) for the lower hips which she	43	86%

Traditional Postpartum Care Practices	Frequency (N=50)	Percent
ideally uses for three months.		
5. From the day of giving birth to the 9 th day, the body is bathed with water whose heat she can tolerate.	42	84%
6. Refrains from eating foods which cause itch like gabi, labong (for at least 5-7 months respectively) or any food seasoned with bagoong.	41	82%
7. From day of delivery to the 17 th day following delivery, she bathes with water nourished with herbs or <i>talbos</i> (like dangla, guava, etc.).	39	78%
8. From day of delivery and henceforth before taking a bath, she is massaged with oil by the hilot, especially on areas like the abdomen, hands, feet, back and also the veins.	39	78%
9. From the 10 th to the 14 th day, the head and body are bathed.	38	76%
10. Refrains from eating ripened langka or jackfruit, preferably for a year.	36	72%
11. Refrains from eating foods which are sour.	35	70%
12. Maintains erect posture especially when eating (feet together on level position and with the back straight).	35	70%
13. Practices <i>sidor</i> or <i>su-ub</i> .	35	70%
14. From day of delivery to utmost two days, she eats malunggay dipped in salt	34	68%
15. Stays in a room that is dark, with curtains undrawn and with only little air/wind coming in.	32	64%
16. Drinks lukewarm water nourished with herbs (<i>pan-nig-an</i> , <i>subusob</i> , <i>putong balat</i>) from day of delivery to utmost 15 days	31	62%
17. Bathes with cold water on the 17 th day	28	56%
18. Refrains from eating eggplant and coconut, linga, peanuts or any food with heavy protein content	27	54%
19. Drinks water only regularly (does not go beyond what is prescribed)	25	50%
20. Refrains from bathing on the 15 th -16 th days (" <i>tinnib</i> ")	24	48%
21. Wears a piece of cloth tied around the forehead	20	40%
22. Has a stove (<i>dalican</i>) nearby where she can get herself warmed from time to time	19	38%

The table above is presented to show which among the Ilocano traditional practices on postpartum care are adhered to by most of the respondents. Based on the table, it appears that the respondents still adhered to most of the practices in the checklist. Out of the 22 practices presented, 13 practices were adhered to by 70% or more of the respondents, while 19 practices were adhered to by 50% or more of the respondents.

On top of the list of practices being adhered to by almost all of the respondents are taking a complete rest by avoiding reading, sewing, routine work, and carrying of anything heavy (96%) and eating foods rich in vitamins especially lean meat, stew, and *tulya* (94%). The adherence to them by most of the respondents implies that the respondents recognized the health risks posed by childbirth that even doing simple household chores could do the mother harm. Since the woman's body is exhausted after going through childbirth, there is a certain expectation that she be excused from doing any household chore in order for her to regain back her energy. Taking a complete rest is a common prescription when someone is sick, more so after childbirth. During pregnancy, a woman's body changes drastically and this is culminated by the birth of her baby. Medical experts say that a woman's body also needs nine whole months to go back to normal. While physically recovering from childbirth, she is also the primary carer of her infant. While other members of the family may extend a helping hand in caring for the infant, it is not possible to delegate breastfeeding to anyone. Breastfeeding alone eats up a lot of energy. Since the woman's body is also the direct source of the baby's nourishment through breastfeeding, the new mother's dietary requirements include foods that nourish her body and that of her infant's. There is also a prevalent belief among Ilocano women that eating foods rich in vitamins like lean meat, stew, and *tulya* stimulate the mammary glands for increased milk production.

Other practices that are adhered to by most of the respondents are the following (80% or more): Use of long skirt and long sleeved blouse, pajama, shawl (*rutap*) and bandana or head gear (88%); wearing of belt (*barikis/calso*) for the stomach/abdomen for at least five months, and a belt/girdle (*patapat/it-it*) for the lower hips for three months (86%), bathing only the body with water whose heat she can tolerate for the first nine days after giving birth (84%); and refraining from eating foods which cause

itch like *gabi*, *labong* (for at least 5-7 months respectively) or any food seasoned with *bagoong* (82%); bathing with water nourished with herbs like *dangla* and *guava* from the day of delivery to the 17th day after giving birth (78%); bathing of the body and head from the 10th to the 14th day (76%); refraining from eating ripened *langka* or jackfruit, preferably for a year (72%); refraining from eating foods which are sour (70%); maintaining erect posture especially when eating (70%); practicing *sidor* or *su-ub* (70%); eating *malunggay* dipped in salt from day of delivery to utmost two days (68%); staying in a dark room with little air coming in (64%); and drinking of lukewarm water nourished with herbs (*pan-nig-an*, *subusob*, *putong balat*) from day of delivery to utmost 15 days (62%).

Reasons for adherence to tanggad

A careful study of the traditional postpartum care practices adhered to by most respondents showed that their adherence to a practice depends upon the actual or perceived benefits that they derive from it. One of which is **health benefit** for the mother. For instance, among those who adhered to taking a complete rest and covering up the body with long or extra layer of clothing, they did so primarily because of the belief that such practices could help them regain their strength (29 out of 48) or prevent the development of varicose veins and/or *rayuma* (29 out of 44). Among those who refrained from eating foods that cause itch like *gabi*, *labong* or food seasoned with *bagoong*, they did so primarily to prevent the occurrence of vaginal itch (31 out of 41). Eating sour foods is also avoided because of the belief that it could cause gastritis (20 of 35). Some bathing prescriptions are also believed to regulate body temperature.

Second, some practices are adhered to because of the belief that they have **health benefits for the infant**. For instance, among those who adhered to eating foods rich in vitamins, they did so because of the belief that eating these foods will increase their milk production and hence, beneficial for the baby's nourishment through breastfeeding (30 out of 47). Some dietary proscriptions like the avoidance of eating sour foods and protein-rich foods are also adhered to because of the belief that these could cause stomach ache and *beri-beri* for the baby.

Third reason revolves around the woman's **desire to get back to normal shape**. Among those who wore belt (*barikis/calso*) for the stomach/abdomen and belt/girdle (*patapat/it-it*) for the lower hips, they did so primarily because of the belief that it could help regain the normal shape of one's body (27 out of 43). Similarly, the respondents who adhered to maintaining erect posture especially when eating did it to prevent the development of an unbalanced figure (20 out of 35).

Lastly, others cited **personal hygiene** as reasons for adhering to a practice. Those who adhered to the practice of bathing the body with hot or lukewarm water from the day of giving birth to the ninth day did so to keep the body fresh from the odour emitted by the genitals (30 out of 42). In addition, eating ripened *langka* or jackfruit is avoided preferably for a year to keep urine from emitting foul odor (28 out of 36).

Reasons for non-adherence to tanggad

This study also looked into the traditional postpartum care practices that are not very much popular among the respondents and the reasons that the respondents provided for not adhering to the practices. It can be observed in Table 7 that no postpartum practice was adhered to by all respondents. Also, some practices were adhered by only less than 50% of the respondents. The respondents gave varied reasons for not adhering to the postpartum care practices. One reason provided is **lack of awareness about the practice** because no one told them about it [R24: *I am not aware of this practice*; R5: *I was not advised by the one who assisted me*; R1: *My mother did not tell me about it*; R2: *Never heard this kind of postpartum care.*] This means that the traditional practice was not passed on to them by the elder members of the family. Based on their responses, there is an expectation for their elders, especially their mothers, to be the ones responsible for passing on to them these traditional postpartum care practices. This is probably one reason why some respondents did not acknowledge these as a family practice [R28: *Not a family practice*; R20: *It is not our practice*; R37: *Elders did not introduce this practice to me.*] Studies show that one cause of the death of a tradition is when one generation fails to pass it on to the next generation.

Another recurring reason for non-adherence to the postpartum care practices is the **influence of medical prescriptions** from health experts and organizations. These prenatal and postnatal prescriptions are heavily disseminated among pregnant women, starting from the barangay level. It seems that when there is an inconsistency between the medical prescriptions and traditional practices, the former usually prevails [R11: *Doctors advise I go back to normal showering*; R2: *My OB Gyne did not prescribe how much water intake after giving birth*; R3: *Doctors say I can eat anything/everything*]. Even the place and method of delivery appears to have a bearing on the decision to deviate from the traditional practices. For instance, if the

mother delivered her baby in the hospital, there is a higher tendency for the mother to follow her doctor's advice than adhere to traditional postpartum care practices. More so if the delivery is through Ceasarian section, which is not performed in any traditional childbirth. These reasons for non-adherence could be clearly illustrated in the following statements from respondents: R20: *Gave birth at the hospital*; R24: *Once I was discharged from the hospital, I already bathed my whole body (head and body)*; R23: [Delivered through] CS. Part of the protocol in any hospital or clinic is the constant monitoring of medical prescriptions given to their patients. In fact, a mother who is discharged from the hospital after delivery is asked to go back for follow up check-up to assess her postnatal progress and to make sure that all medical prescriptions are followed closely.

For some, they cited **inconvenience or impracticality of the practice** as a reason for non-adherence. They attributed this to the inaccessibility of some needed resources to carry out the practice, the season when they gave birth, and the discomfort of following these practices. [R5: *Availability of the herbs needed and good manghihilot*; R28: *No stove (dalican)...*; R2: *I gave birth during summer. Too hot if one uses long skirt, long sleeve blouse, etc.*; R23: *Hot. I can't stand that feeling if it's very hot*; R12: *It would have been very uncomfortable not to take a bath after a few days of giving birth.*] These days, only a few households have *dalicans*, and even good *hilots* are hard to find. It is not surprising therefore that the use of *dalican* during the postpartum period recorded the lowest adherence (38%). Unlike before, many of the prescribed herbs for bathing and drinking are not readily available in people's backyards now. Bayombong may not be a highly urbanized place, but economic and social developments are evident in people's occupation, living spaces, and household necessities. It is probably because of these environmental changes why some respondents found some practices to be inconvenient or impractical to follow.

Lastly, some respondents explicitly said that they **do not believe in the effectiveness** of the practice - despite being aware of it, having been told about it, and having the means to practice it. This implies that there is an obvious disregard of the practices. [R21: *I do not believe in it*; R27: *It's awkward*; R37: *I do not like this practice*; R23: *Unhygienic*; R25: *I just did not practice it.*] Apparently, this obvious disregard of some practices stemmed from their own personal concept of what is beneficial or not to them in terms of their overall wellbeing. One example is the wearing of a piece of cloth tied around the forehead, adhered to by only 40% of the respondents, who found the practice to be "uncomfortable" and "awkward." Many respondents also found some bathing prescriptions to be "unhygienic" and they "did not believe" in some dietary requirements either. It is important to note that the respondents are all educated as evidenced by their employment in legitimate organizations, and their knowledge acquired through education and their exposure to a modern world may have influenced their perception of what postpartum care practices are beneficial or not to them. After all, they are at the center of these postpartum care practices.

Modifications of traditional postpartum care practices

While it is true that many of the traditional postpartum care practices are still adhered to by more than half of the respondents (50% and above), the researchers also observed some respondents who indicated **modifications** to these practices. One example of which is the eating of *malunggay* dipped in salt from day of delivery to utmost two days, which was adhered to by 68% of the respondents. One respondent admitted adhering to this practice but instead of just dipping the *malunggay* in salt, she said that the *malunggay* was boiled and dipped in salt and tinola [R4: *...boiled malunggay dipped in salt and tinola.*] Another respondent remarked that during her confinement period, the room she stayed in was not totally dark [R28: *Not totally dark room; curtains withdrawn but with little air.*] The length of time by which the girdle or belt is worn was also modified by some respondents, who claimed to have worn it only for a few days or weeks [R20: *I only used it for a few days*; R10: *Wore it only after a few weeks of delivery.*] The bathing prescriptions were also modified, with a good number of respondents saying that they indeed took a bath daily, the head included [R2: *Body including head with warm water*; R3: *Head and body are bathed for personal hygiene*; R8: *Usually takes a bath after a few days only after giving birth then resume to normal routine.*] The modifications are maybe due to the inconvenience of following exactly the prescriptions since the respondents are limited by time, work, changing values, and even budget, a scenario which also came out in the study of Gatan (1990).

The modifications may have stemmed from changing values and situations, confluence of cultures due to intermarriages and local migration, and evolving economic and sociocultural landscapes. These are all part of the challenges that confront the Ilocano working woman in relation to her practice of *tanggap*.

All in all, it is still safe to say that many of the Ilocano postpartum care practices are adhered to by the majority of the respondents. They rely on their elders to pass on these traditional practices to them,

and it is assumed that they would pass it on to the next generation after them. Many of these traditional postpartum care practices revolved around the physical recovery of the woman and her baby, but these are extended to her mental wellbeing as well. The participation of the other members of the family like the husband, mother, and mother-in-law in the observance of *tanggad* is an indication of social support that is afforded to the woman. Even health organizations encourage this kind of family support to keep the woman from going through postpartum depression, a health condition which was initially dismissed as a minor condition but now has gained medical attention (WHO, 2015). These are probably reasons why, even if some practices do not seem to have medical value, these practices are still adhered to by many even up to this day. This study also took note of an increasing number of respondents who sought logical explanations for the traditional postpartum practices. Oftentimes, they sought answers from health experts and organizations whose postnatal care prescriptions sometimes showed deviations from the traditional practices. It is safe to say then that many of the respondents do not just blindly follow traditions because they are also aware of the reasons behind such practice. Interestingly, many of the reasons cited for following such practices are linked to acceptable medical practices such as taking a complete rest and eating foods rich in vitamins. This only means that traditional and modern ways of postpartum care practices could co-exist. Tradition and science just need to strike a balance about practices that are beneficial and not beneficial to the woman. After all, the purpose of the two is the same which is the overall wellbeing of the mother.

Section 2: Challenges in the Practice of *Tanggad*

The challenges that the respondents encountered in the practice of *tanggad* were also sought. The past and present economic and sociocultural contexts of pregnancy and childbirth and the impact of these on the woman's decision to adhere to traditional postpartum care practices were looked into. Before, most women gave birth in their homes because of the far distance, or even absence, of hospitals or birthing clinics from their homes. These women were assisted by the *hilots* or an elder woman of the family, usually the mother or mother-in-law. Because of the inaccessibility of the hospital, prenatal assessment was also performed by the *hilot*. The length of the woman's confinement period is not dictated by any labor mandate as she is not employed in a formal organization governed by labor laws and policies. At present, an employed pregnant woman is required by law to submit a proof of her pregnancy during the first trimester. The proof includes the formal confirmation of a medical doctor/obstetrician after the conduct of physical examination to the pregnant woman, or through an ultrasound performed by a medical practitioner. If these are not submitted, she may not be able to enjoy fully her maternity benefits. During these prenatal visits, postpartum care prescriptions are also discussed with the woman. All these, and more, may pose a challenge in her continued observance of *tanggad*.

Table 8

Challenges in the practice of tanggad

Challenges in the Practice of <i>Tanggad</i>		
A. Changing values/attitudes/situations	Does: 42	84%
	Does Not: 8	16%
1. Indifference towards properly observing the tradition because of the influence of modern medicine	39	93
2. Status requires one to consult a physician more than the folk practitioner	20	48
3. Tendency to forego practice because of modern advancement	16	38
4. Tendency to waive other practices for fear of being called "product of bygone times"	8	19
5. Elders who know the practices on postpartum care are not around or not available because they are either working or living in a different place	11	26
6. The health department campaign does not include the traditional practices in their promotions	9	21
B. Interference of Work	Does: 38	76%
	Does Not: 12	24%
1. Nature of position held	21	55
2. Work assignments may keep one from observing the tradition religiously	17	45
3. Bulk of work cuts off observance of other practices because of the desire	15	39

to get back to work		
4. Other reasons	1	4
C. Time element	Does: 34 Does Not: 16	68% 32%
1. Time schedule is too taxing.	7	21
2. Duration in which the process takes place is too lengthy.	14	41
3. Practices involved in the process are time consuming.	13	38
4. Practices involved are too rigid.	7	21
5. Duration of maternity leave is inadequate to meet the requirements of the process.	9	26
6. Other reasons	1	3
D. Budgetary Constraints	Does: 26 Does Not: 24	52% 48%
1. Socio-economic status may hinder the religious observance of the tradition.	10	38
2. Compensation received may not suffice in the maintenance of mother's needs/requirements of the process.	12	46
3. Person involved does not have other sources of income thus interfering in the observance of the process	11	42

In this study, the Ilocano working women in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya were chosen as respondents because they are the ones who are directly challenged by the evolving postnatal care practices. As educated working women, they are predisposed to rationalize their actions based on logic and science. They are bound by their employment contracts and organizational policies, and they are exposed to a variety of cultures in their immediate environment. All these may pose a challenge in their continued practice of their traditions. Four challenges in the practice of *tanggap* were identified, arranged according to the number of respondents who reported having been challenged by each in their practice of *tanggap*: changing values and situations (84%), work interference (76%), time element (68%), and budgetary constraints (52%).

Changing values and situations

Eighty four percent (84%) of the respondents reported having been challenged by changing values and situations - the first on the list - in their practice of *tanggap*. Of this number, almost all (39 out of 42) indicated becoming indifferent towards properly observing the tradition because of the influence of modern medicine. The influence of modern medicine cannot be disregarded, especially that the respondents attended formal schooling where modern and scientific ways of responding to health problems are discussed. The vast influence of modern medicine on the health decisions of the respondents also surfaced in Section I of this study. The health department in the Philippines also has policies on regular prenatal and postnatal check-ups during which modern method of postnatal care is discussed with the woman. Another factor, though reported by only less than half (20 out of 42) of the respondents, is status. The respondents said that their status required them to consult a physician more than the folk practitioner. In almost all organizations, maternity benefits are only made available if the pregnant woman shows proof that she consulted an accredited physician to confirm her pregnancy, which is done through prenatal visits to an OB Gyne. The duration of her recovery is also determined by the government-approved length of maternity leave that all public and private organizations are mandated to enforce. At present, the newly approved duration of maternity leave with pay is 105 days (<http://www.csc.gov.ph/new-updates/1911-govtissuesclaificationon105maternityleave.html>) during which the woman is expected to recuperate.

Interference of work

Interference of work comes next, which was reported by 76% of the respondents. A little more than half (21 out of 38) of them indicated that they were challenged by the nature of position that they hold in their work, while close to half (45%) said that work assignments may keep them from observing the tradition religiously. As cited above, a woman's employment may interfere with the observance of postpartum care practices because of certain expectations that spring from a woman's position in her organization. As mentioned earlier, maternity benefits are linked to certain labor standards that one must comply with in order to avail of certain work benefits. When a woman is employed, it is expected that she abides by these expectations, more so if the woman occupies a high position in the organization. Also,

some job policies related to work schedule, place of work, and even prescribed uniforms or attire may keep one from observing these traditional postpartum practices. For instance, the expected physical mobility of the woman in performing her work and the policies related to the wearing of prescribed uniforms may interfere with the wearing of belt (*barikis*) or girdle (*patapat*) around the stomach and the lower hips for at least three to five months.

Time element

Third challenge is time element which was reported by 68% of the respondents. It appears that the respondents were also challenged by the duration in which the process of postpartum care takes place, described by some as too lengthy (14 out of 34). Some traditional postpartum care practices take months to complete, while the government-approved maternity leave in the Philippines is only 105 days based on RA 11210, better known as the 105-Day Expanded Maternity Leave Law (<http://www.csc.gov.ph/new-updates/1911-govtissuesclaificationon105maternityleave.html>). Therefore, even if there is a desire to follow the tradition, the respondents are limited by the duration required of them to do so, which was also described by some as time consuming (13 out of 34).

Budgetary Constraints

Lastly, budgetary constraint was reported by 52% of the respondents as a challenge in their practice of *tanggap*. This means that among the four challenges that may pose a problem in the observance of *tanggap*, budgetary constraint is the least problem for them. This is probably because many of the practices related to *tanggap* do not require expensive resources to perform. Many of the resources and ingredients needed in the observance of *tanggap* are easy to find in the immediate environment. Some of the woman's dietary requirements are composed of foods that are commonly sold in public markets at reasonable prices. The clothing prescriptions are not expensive either. It is also safe to say that the respondents have the financial means to afford the minimal cost of *tanggap* since they have a steady source of income courtesy of their employment. These are possible reasons why budgetary constraints ranked last among the challenges in the practice of *tanggap*.

As shown in the discussion above, the Ilocano working women in Bayombong are constantly challenged by many factors in the observance of *tanggap*. These factors may have emanated from the changes in perception and values that the woman herself has gone through, changes in labor policies pertaining to women welfare, workplace guidelines, modern medical prescriptions on postpartum care, and other societal changes. The impact of these challenges could be seen in the increased scrutiny of the traditional postpartum care practices by the woman herself before these are adhered to. In cases where there are doubts about the value or benefit of a traditional postpartum care practice, modern medical guidelines are sought for direction. The next section presents which among the postpartum care practices or *tanggap* have medical value based on the recommendation of a global health organization.

Section 3: Scientific Foundations of the Traditional Postpartum Practices

Table 9

Comparison of tanggad and the WHO guidelines on postnatal care

Ilocano Traditional Postpartum Care Practices	Respondents who Adhered to the Practice	Stand of WHO about the Practice	Contents of the WHO Postnatal Care Guidelines (2013 and 2015)
1. Takes complete rest	96%	Recommended	To have enough rest and sleep; to avoid hard physical work (WHO, 2015)
2. Eats foods rich in vitamins	94%	Recommended	Eat a greater amount and variety of healthy foods (WHO, 2015)
3. Eats malunggay dipped in salt	68%	Recommended	Eat a greater amount and variety of healthy foods (WHO, 2015)
4. Bathes only the body with lukewarm water for 9 days after delivery	84%	Partly recommended but with deviation	Wash the body daily; Wash all over daily, particularly the perineum; wash hands before handling baby
5. Bathes with water	78%	Partly	Wash the body daily; Wash all over

Ilocano Traditional Postpartum Care Practices	Respondents who Adhered to the Practice	Stand of WHO about the Practice	Contents of the WHO Postnatal Care Guidelines (2013 and 2015)
nourished with herbs		recommended but with deviation	daily, particularly the perineum; wash hands before handling baby
6. Bathing of the body and head from the 10 th to the 14 th day	76%	Partly recommended but with deviation	Wash the body daily; Wash all over daily, particularly the perineum; wash hands before handling baby
7. Drinks lukewarm water nourished with herbs	62%	Partly recommended but with deviation	Drink plenty of clean and safe water
8. Bathes with cold water on the 17 th day	56%	Partly recommended but with deviation	Drink plenty of clean and safe water
9. Drinks water only regularly	50%	Partly recommended but with deviation	Drink plenty of clean and safe water
10. Refrains from eating foods which cause itch	82%	Not recommended	The mother can eat any normal foods (WHO, 2015)
11. Refrains from eating ripened langka or jackfruit	72%	Not recommended	The mother can eat any normal foods (WHO, 2015)
12. Refrains from eating foods which are sour	70%	Not recommended	The mother can eat any normal foods (WHO, 2015)
13. Refrains from eating food with heavy protein content	54%	Not recommended	The mother can eat any normal foods (WHO, 2015)
14. Refrains from bathing on the 15 th - 16 th days ("tinnib")	48%	Not recommended	The mother can eat any normal foods (WHO, 2015)
15. Maintains erect posture especially when eating	70%	Partly recommended with deviation	No mention of it in the WHO guidelines
16. Uses extra body covering (rutap)	88%	Neither recommend nor prohibit	No mention of it in the WHO guidelines
17. Wears belt (<i>barikis/calso</i>) and a belt/girdle (<i>patapat/it-it</i>)	86%	Neither recommend nor prohibit	No mention of it in the WHO guidelines
18. Being massaged with oil by a hilot	78%	Neither recommend nor prohibit	No mention of it in the WHO guidelines
19. Practices <i>sidor</i> or <i>su-ub</i>	70%	Neither recommend nor prohibit	No mention of it in the WHO guidelines
20. Stays in a dark room with little ventilation	64%	Neither recommend nor prohibit	No mention of it in the WHO guidelines
21. Wears a piece of cloth tied around the forehead	40%	Neither recommend nor prohibit	No mention of it in the WHO guidelines
22. Has a stove (<i>dalican</i>) to warm herself	38%	Neither recommend nor prohibit	No mention of it in the WHO guidelines

The traditional postpartum care practices related to *tanggap* were compared with the guidelines and recommendations on maternal and postnatal care advanced by the World Health Organization. In this particular study, the traditional postpartum care practices, 22 all in all, were compared with WHO's 2013 postnatal care for mothers and newborns and WHO's 2015 guide for essential practice on pregnancy, childbirth, postpartum, and newborn care. The purpose is to determine which traditional practices could co-exist with Western health models for a comprehensive and encompassing health campaign that incorporates both cultural and medical dimensions.

The traditional practices were labelled as recommended, partly recommended with deviation, discouraged, neither recommend nor discourage.

Recommended practices

It is interesting to note that three of the traditional Ilocano postnatal practices also appeared in the WHO guidelines. Two of the three practices are also the top two practices that the respondents adhered to the most. The first one - taking a complete rest - was adhered to by 96% of the respondents. In the traditional practice, complete rest includes the avoidance of reading, sewing, carrying of anything heavy and doing any routine housework. The 2013 WHO guidelines advise women to have enough rest and sleep. Part of the recommended counselling that health workers must do is to advise women in the postpartum period to avoid strenuous physical work. However, it is not supposed to be a total immobility because the WHO guidelines indicate that "all women should be encouraged to mobilize as soon as appropriate following the birth. They should be encouraged to take gentle exercise and make time to rest during the postnatal period" (p. 7). Complete rest is recommended for obvious reasons. The woman's body has undergone physical trauma due to childbirth so rest and sleep are needed for the body to recover fast.

Eating nutritious foods, which was adhered to by 94% of the respondents, also appeared in the WHO recommendations. In the 2015 WHO guidelines, health workers are instructed to provide counsel on nutrition by advising women to "eat greater amount and variety of healthy foods such as meat, fish, oils, coconut, nuts, cereals, beans, vegetables, fruits, cheese, and milk" (p. 89). These recommendations are meant for the woman's speedy recovery and for her baby's health. Since breastfeeding is the only source of the baby's nutrition during the first six months of birth (WHO, 2013), the mother must see to it that she is nourished well by eating foods rich in vitamins. It follows that the traditional practice of eating *malunggay* dipped in salt during the postpartum period, adhered to by 68% of the respondents, is also recommended by WHO because *malunggay* is a good source of nutrition as found in many studies.

Partly recommended practices with deviation

Some practices are partly recommended by WHO. These practices are labelled as partly recommended because they appeared in the guidelines but showed deviations from the WHO guidelines. Bathing practices fall under this category. The WHO guidelines emphasized the daily washing of the body or washing all over particularly the perineum and regular hand washing for postnatal and infant care. The woman is advised to wash all over daily to avoid infection especially if the woman has experienced severe perineal tear. On top of that, she has to observe proper hand washing to make sure that she is clean when she holds her baby. These WHO guidelines show similarities to *tanggap* bathing prescriptions, but there are deviations. In *tanggap*, only the body, excluding the head, is bathed during the first nine days following delivery. The head is only bathed on the 10th to 14th day; no bathing on the 15th to 16th day; starts to bathe with cold water on the 17th day. Before the 17th day, only tolerable hot water nourished with herbs must be used. The WHO guidelines advised women to wash all over daily; it did not say that the head should not be washed for several days. It did not indicate whether the water is hot, cold, or nourished with herbs. What is emphasized is the observance of proper hygiene which can be achieved through daily bath and regular hand washing.

Prescriptions regarding the drinking of water also appeared in both traditional practice and the WHO guidelines. The traditional practices stipulate that the woman should regularly drink water that is lukewarm and nourished with herbs. The WHO advised women to drink plenty of clean, safe water – no other recommendation whatsoever but just water that is safe to drink.

Discouraged practices

Some practices though are explicitly discouraged by WHO. Most of these practices revolved around diet and nutrition during the postpartum period. In *tanggap*, the woman is advised not to eat sour foods, protein-heavy foods, *langka* or jackfruit, and foods that are believed to cause itch. It is believed that eating these foods would pose danger to the health of the mother and baby by causing beri-beri, stomach

ache, and itchy skin, among others. These are in contrast with the WHO guidelines which stipulated that the woman is allowed to eat any normal food. The foods prohibited in the traditional practice are considered normal foods which are part of the Ilocano's daily diet. The WHO guidelines assured the mother that she "can eat any normal foods and that these foods will not harm the breastfeeding baby" (WHO, 2015, p. 89). In addition, the WHO also instructed health practitioners to determine if there are important taboos about foods which are nutritionally healthy so that the woman is advised against these taboos.

Neither recommended nor discouraged practices

Many of the traditional practices on postpartum care did not appear in the WHO guidelines. This does not necessarily mean that the practice of such should be discontinued. It only means that there are no scientific evidences yet as to the value or lack of value of the practices, at least when WHO is concerned. The continued practice of such then is left to the woman concerned because there are no medical evidences available to say that these practices are harmful or harmless to the mother and the baby. Such practices include the use of extra body covering (*rutap*), wearing of belt or girdle (*barikis/calso/patapat/it-it*), being massaged with oil by a *hilot*, practice of *sidor/suob* (steam), staying in a dark room with little ventilation, wearing of a piece of cloth around the forehead, and the use of *dalican* to warm oneself.

Covering up the body with long skirts, pajamas, and *rutap* - adhered to by 88% of the respondents - is widely believed by the respondents to prevent the penetration of air into the pores. Accordingly, if the air penetrates into the pores, the woman may develop varicose veins and *rayuma*. The absence of such prescription in the WHO guidelines does not mean that this practice has no value. Otherwise, WHO should have stated its discontinuance, like what it did with some of the *tanggad* dietary prescriptions which posed direct danger to the wellbeing of the mother. The same is true with the other traditional Ilocano postpartum care practices which did not appear in the WHO guidelines. The practice of such may not have a direct bearing on the physical recovery of the mother, but as one respondent has said, "There is nothing wrong when one follows traditions" (R: 37). After all, our traditions define our identity as a people, and by adhering to the practices, we also manifest our oneness with our kind. As pointed out by Gatan (1990), the value of *tanggad* also lies in the psychosocial support that it provides the mother-infant unit. In fact, the WHO has provided leeway for adjustments in some of its guidelines to accommodate the cultural context where some practices are coming from. An example is the guideline on delaying the bathing babies until 24 hours after birth, which may be adjusted to at least 6 hours if 24 hours is not possible due to cultural reasons (WHO, 2013).

The foregoing discussion shows that traditions and science can co-exist in the practice of *tanggad*. There may be some areas where they do not meet eye to eye, but their objective is always the same and that is the mother's welfare. Both are important elements of the society - science for spearheading many medical breakthroughs that made our lives easier than before, and tradition for its contribution to people's deeper understanding of who they are in order to become a socially functional member of a society. However, part of this co-existence also includes an evaluation of the practices that are detrimental to the mother and the baby for a holistic approach to postnatal care.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Many of the Ilocano traditional postpartum care practices, or *tanggad* in the Ilocano parlance, are still adhered to by the Ilocano working women in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. The practices that are adhered to by a greater number of the respondents are those practices which are also advanced by health experts, those that do not require much effort to do, and those practices whose needed resources are easy to find in the immediate environment. The adherence to these prescriptions does not just stem from a woman's oblivious observance of the perceived effectiveness of her culture's practices, but it also springs from her critical assessment of the effectiveness of the practice for her speedy physical recovery. The Ilocano working woman has evolved over time as shown in her adherence to *tanggad*. As a working woman in a place described as a meeting place of many cultures, she is both challenged by social expectations and cultural diversity in her observance of *tanggad*.

The adherence to the traditional postpartum care is not solely based on the medical value that one derives from it. As found in this study, many of the respondents still adhered to the practices even if these are not advanced by health organizations because of the social support and sense of belongingness that they get from adhering to their traditional practices. Interestingly, this social support is also highlighted in the WHO recommendations in order to address the mental health of the woman during this critical time of her recovery. Therefore, the value of *tanggad* should not be solely evaluated by its

contribution to the physical recovery of the woman, rather to its overall contribution to the woman's general wellbeing especially her mental and emotional health.

To further enrich this study, other medical guidelines on postnatal care - aside from those recommended by WHO – may be sought to widen the discussion of the medical bearing of *tanggap* on the woman's physical and psychological wellbeing.

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XIII. Project Timetable

Activity	Duration	Start/Completion Dates
Full blown proposal	1 month	September 2019
Data gathering	2 months	October-November 2019
Data encoding	2 weeks	November 2019
Data analysis	1 month	December 2019
Writing of research report	1 month	January 2020
Oral presentation/Dissemination	Faculty Research Forum 2 nd Batch	November 19, 2020
Finalize full paper	One week	
Submission of Final Paper	1 day	November 27, 2020
Dissemination/Publication	Year 3	

XIV. Signatories

Dr. Clara M. Gonzales
Lead Researcher

Mrs. Rosalie C. Carreon
Collaborator

Mr. Brent Jericko P. Narciso
Collaborator

Dr. Zayda S. Asuncion
Collaborator

Recommending Approval:

Fe Yolanda G. del Rosario, PhD
Dean, School of Teacher Education and Humanities

Darwin Don M. Dacles, PhD
Director, University Research Center

Approved by:

John Octavious S. Palina, PhD
University President

INFORMED CONSENT

PURPOSE AND BACKGROUND. The undersigned are conducting a research on **Traditional Beliefs and Practices on Postpartum Care in a Rural Community in the Philippines: Towards a Multidisciplinary Practice of Postpartum Care**. The purpose of the study is to surface the traditional practices related to postpartum care as practiced by working Ilocano mothers.

PROCEDURES. If you agree to participate in this research study, you will be asked to accomplish a survey checklist, with few personal information required (though name is optional).

CONFIDENTIALITY. The records from this study will be kept confidential. No individual identities will be used in any reports or publications resulting from the study. All questionnaires will be given codes and stored separately from any names or other direct identification of participants. After the study, all accomplished questionnaires will be stored for a year before these will be destroyed

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION. Your decision whether or not to participate in this study is voluntary. If you choose to participate in this study, you can withdraw your consent and discontinue participation at any time without prejudice.

QUESTIONS. If you have any questions about the study, please contact us through SMU number 321-2222.

CONSENT

You are making a decision whether or not to participate in a research study. Your signature below indicates that you have decided to participate in the study after reading all the information above and you understand the information in this form, have had any questions answered, and have received a copy of this form for you to keep upon request.

Name and Signature of Participant/Respondent: _____ Date _____

Name and Signature of Researchers: _____ Date: _____

Saint Mary's University
Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

October 6, 2019

Dear respondent,

Marian greetings!

We are conducting a study titled "Traditional Beliefs and Practices on Postpartum Care in a Rural Community in the Philippines: Towards a Multidisciplinary Practice of Postpartum Care." We have chosen you as one of our respondents. Please accomplish the following checklist as honestly as possible. Rest assured that your answers will remain confidential and will only be used for the purpose of this study. Thank you very much.

Respectfully yours,

Clara M. Gonzales
Rosalie Navoa
Brent Jericko Narciso
Zayda Asuncion

Name: _____ Age: _____ Number of Children: _____
Occupation: _____ Position: _____ Administrative _____
Rank-and-File _____

PRACTICES ASSOCIATED WITH TANGGAD.

Directions. Here is a list of practices associated with Ilocano postpartum care in the observance of "tanggad". Put a check mark (/) before the item on those that you observe, then encircle the letter/s of the reasons behind it. If you don't observe the practice, put an x mark before the item and write the reason/s for not observing it in the space provided.

I. On physical setting

- _____ A. Stays in a room that is dark, with curtains undrawn and with only little air/wind coming in...
7. To prevent the occurrence of gastric disorders/discomfort
 8. To prevent the occurrence of beri-beri (*ib-bal*)
 9. To enable the return to normalcy of skin color
 10. To prevent one from relapsing
 11. Other reasons: _____

- _____ B. Has a stove (*dalican*) nearby where he can get herself warmed from time to time

7. To prevent the occurrence of gastric disorders/discomfort
8. To prevent the occurrence of beri-beri (*ib-bal*)
9. To drive devil spirits away
10. To neutralize the odor emitted during delivery
11. Other reasons: _____

II. On what to use

- _____ A. Uses long skirt and long sleeved blouse, pajama, shawl (*rutap*) and bandana or head gear...

6. To facilitate convenience in breastfeeding
7. To facilitate convenience in changing clothes
8. To prevent the penetration of air into the pores thus preventing development of varicose veins and/or *rayuma*.
9. Other reason: _____

- _____ B. Wears belt (*barikis/calso*) for the stomach/abdomen which she uses for at least 5 months, and a belt/girdle (*patapat/it-it*) for the lower hips which she ideally uses for three months.

8. To prevent the occurrence of abdominal and back pains
9. To prevent gastric disorders/disturbances especially since the baby has just been delivered

10. To prevent blood from flowing excessively
11. To prevent the mother from bleeding profusely
12. To help regain the normal shape of one's body
13. Other reasons: _____

- _____ C. Wears a piece of cloth tied around the forehead
6. To help sustain strength especially right after delivery
 7. To prevent dizziness thereby helping in the maintenance of body equilibrium
 8. To prevent involuntary "nodding" of head
 9. Other reasons: _____

III. On physical hygiene

_____ A. From day of giving birth to the 9th day, the body is bathed with water whose heat she can tolerate

6. To prevent from impurities from rushing to the head
7. To serve as body regulator
8. For personal hygiene (keep body fresh from odor emitted by the genitals)
9. Other reasons: _____

- _____ B. From the 10th-14th day, the head and body are bathed
5. To allow blood regulation
 6. Adaption of the body to normal/usual body temperature
 7. Other reasons: _____

- _____ C. Refrains from bathing on the 15th-16th days ("tinnib")
5. To adjust oneself to temperature
 6. To keep body heat regulated
 7. Other reasons: _____

- _____ D. Bathes with cold water on the 17th day
5. To allow for return to usual hygienic routine
 6. To test the body for any allergies
 7. Other reasons: _____

_____ E. From day of delivery to the 17th day following delivery, she bathes with water nourished with herbs or talbos (like dangla, guava, etc.)

6. To prevent one from relapsing
7. To facilitate healing effect on uterus
8. To serve as soothing balm for the skin
9. Other reasons: _____

IV. On what to take in

_____ A. Drinks lukewarm water nourished with herbs (pan-nig-an, subusob, putong balat) from day of delivery to utmost 15 days

6. For easy healing of internal wound
7. To prevent gastric pain
8. To provide strength
9. Other reasons: _____

- _____ B. Drinks water only regularly (does not go beyond what is prescribed)
6. To prevent vomiting
 7. To prevent body tissues
 8. To prevent frequent urinating which might cause the "butilaw" to come out
 9. Other reasons: _____

_____ C. From day of delivery to utmost 2 days, she eat malunggay dipped in salt

6. To nourish the mammary glands
7. To supply vitamin to both the mother and the baby
8. To prevent occurrence of beri-beri (ibbal)
9. Other reasons: _____

_____ D. Eats foods rich in vitamins especially lean meat, stew, tulya, etc.

7. To stimulate the secretion of the mammary glands
8. To provide full nourishment to the baby
9. To keep one strong
10. To help regain usual strength
11. Other reasons: _____

_____ E. Refrains from eating foods which are sour

6. To prevent gastritis
7. It may cause baby's stomachache
8. To prevent clotting of blood impurities (lurayen)
9. Other reasons: _____

_____ F. Refrains from eating foods which cause itch like gabi, labong (for at leasy 5-7 months respectively) or any food seasoned with bagoong.

6. To keep skin clean
7. To prevent occurrence of skin disorders
8. To prevent occurrence of vaginal itch
9. Other reasons: _____

_____ G. Refrains from eating ripened langka or jackfruit, preferably for a year

6. To prevent urinary tract infection
7. To keep urine from emitting foul odor
8. To keep one from relapsing
9. Other reasons: _____

_____ H. Refrains from eating eggplant and coconut, linga, peanuts ir any food with heavy protein content

6. It causes the uterus to come out (butilaw)
7. To prevent occurrence of bri-beri on both mother and the baby
8. To facilitate proper digestion
9. Other reasons: _____

V. On maintenance of energy

_____ A. From day of delivery and henceforth before taking a bath, she is massaged with oil by the hilot, especially on areas like the abdomen, hands, feet, back and also the veins

5. To facilitate the normal position of the ovary
6. To refresh the veins and muscles stretched during delivery
7. Other reasons: _____

_____ B. Takes complete rest (avoids reading, sewing, carrying of anything heavy, routine work)

6. To keep one from relapsing
7. To prevent one from becoming blind (ar-rap)
8. Helps one to easily regain usual strength
9. Other reasons: _____

VI. Other practices

_____ A. Maintains erect posture especially when eating (feet together on level position and with the back straight)

5. Prevents development of an unbalanced figure
6. Soothes muscles especially since mother gets tired easily following delivery
7. Other reasons: _____

_____ B. Practices *sidor* or *su-ub*

5. It serves as soothing balm especially on the genitals
6. To help regulate body heat
7. Other reasons: _____

Please write below other Ilocano postpartum practices that you are familiar with, and the reason behind such practice.

CHALLENGES IN THE PRACTICE OF TANGGAD.

Directions. Below is a list of problems working mothers might experience in the process of observing the “tanggad”. Put a check (/) mark on items which you believe pose a problem, then encircle the letter/s of reasons that make it so. If you feel that they don’t pose any problem at all, just put an X mark in the space before the item. If you think that there are other reasons not mentioned in the choices, write them in the space provided.

_____ A. Time element

7. Time schedule is too taxing.
8. Duration in which the process takes place is too lengthy.
9. Practices involved in the process are time consuming.
10. Practices involved are too rigid.
11. Duration of maternity leave is inadequate to meet the requirements of the process.
12. Other reasons: _____

_____ B. Budgetary Constraints

4. Socio-economic status may hinder the religious observance of the tradition.
5. Compensation received may not suffice in the maintenance of mother’s needs/requirements of the process.
6. Person involved does not have other sources of income thus interfering in the observance of the process
7. Other reasons: _____

_____ C. Interference of Work

5. Nature of position held
6. Work assignments may keep one from observing the tradition religiously
7. Bulk of work cuts off observance of other practices because of the desire to get back to work
8. Other reasons: _____

_____ D. Changing values/attitudes/situations

7. Indifference towards properly observing the tradition because of the influence of modern medicine
8. Status requires one to consult a physician more than the folk practitioner
9. Tendency to forego practice because of modern advancement
10. Tendency to waive other practices for fear of being called “product of bygone times”
11. Elders who know the practices on postpartum care are not around or not available because they are either working or living in a different place
12. The health department campaign do not include the traditional practices in their promotions
13. Other reasons: _____

Please write below other problems/challenges that you have experienced in the observance of tanggad,
